

The Importance of the Motivational Process in Different Periods of Personality Development

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Annotation: In different periods of personality development, the process of motivation is important, as it is one of the main factors motivating a person to achieve goals and change themselves. In adapting to society, a child relies on environmental factors, in particular, the family environment, school, teachers, friends, and other social institutions. In the process of personality development, motivation plays a key role in shaping the social skills of children and youth, setting their own interests and goals. Therefore, the harmonization of the motivational process with socialization and the effective use of technological means are important for the healthy development of personality.

Keywords: personality development, motivation process, socialization, environmental factors, family environment, school and teachers, motivational incentive, goal setting, self-realization, personal growth, internal and external motivation.

Introduction. The concept of personality refers to a person and serves to represent a member of society who is psychologically developed, differs from others in personal characteristics and behavior, has a certain behavior and worldview. In order for a person to become a person, he must develop mentally, feel like a complete person, and differ from others in his characteristics and qualities.

Scientific research on personality development and motivation processes is widely covered in many psychological, pedagogical and sociological sources. This section analyzes the literature on the importance of motivation in different periods of personality development and examines methodological approaches.

There are several basic psychological theories on motivation and personality development. These theories and scientific resources serve as an important basis for studying human motivation.

The theory of the "pyramid of needs" by Abraham Maslow-Maslow (1943) based personality development on the pyramid of needs, arguing that each person primarily has a desire to satisfy basic needs (physical, protective, social). In the process of personality development, motivation is formed primarily on the basis of these needs. According to Maslow's theory, needs at a higher stage (self-realization, creative growth) are realized only after basic needs are met. This theory helps to understand how motivation changes in different periods of personality development.¹

Erik Erikson from the Theory of Psychological Development-Erikson (1950) in his theory of psychosocial development divides personality development into eight stages, showing the importance of individual motivation at each stage. For example, while motivation in childhood and adolescence focuses on introspection and social acceptance, motivation for professional and spiritual success increases in adulthood and middle age. Erickson's theory helps to understand how motivation is formed in accordance with the stages of personality development.

Vygotsky's Theory of social learning - Lev Vygotsky (1978) considers motivation as a social process, emphasizing the role of society and the environment in child development. According to Vygotsky,

¹ Maslow A. H.. *Motivation and Personality*. N. Y.: Harpaer and Row, 1954.

motivation is formed not only by personal internal forces, but also by social influences and stimuli in the environment. The motivational influence of teachers, parents, and peers is of great importance in this process.²

Desi and Ryan's theory of internal and external motivation - Deci and Ryan (1985) examined the difference between internal (autonomy, self-awareness) and external (incentives, rewards) types of motivation. They argue that the formation of internal motivation at different stages of personality development is especially important for self-awareness and the manifestation of one's own abilities. In adolescence and adulthood, intrinsic motivation is of great importance for achieving one's goals and self-realization³.

Carol Dweck's Theory of Self-confidence and Motivation for Growth - Carol Dweck (2006) analyzes a person's approach to success and their own motivation for growth in her concept of growth thinking. According to his theory, people's belief in "intellectual growth" is a key determinant of their success in life. The Door's approach helps to understand the types of motivation that change in different periods of personality development. As for methodology, several methodological approaches can be used to study the process of motivation in different periods of personality development. These methods have been developed mainly on the basis of psychological and pedagogical research.

Experimental methods - experimental research is widely used to study various forms of motivation and their impact on personality development. For example, various stimuli and environmental changes can be included to study the changing motivational processes in children and youth. It uses, for example, reward or incentive systems to study how motivation is formed and develops.

Design and observation methods - in research, changes in motivation at different stages of personality development can also be analyzed using long-term observations. Using this method, it is possible to observe how motivation is related to various social, psychological and cultural factors. Interviews and questionnaires-when studying the place of motivation in personality development through personal interviews and questionnaires, you can get an opinion about motivational factors from people themselves. This method allows you to get detailed information about personal experiences, values, needs, and motivational decisions.

Childhood and adolescence are the most important source of motivation in childhood and adolescence - it is the attention and incentives from parents, teachers and other close people. During this period, external motivation (for example, parental motivation) plays a very important role in the process of self-knowledge of children and adolescents, in determining their own goals and their implementation. To achieve good results, it is important that students are constantly motivated to study well, excel in sports, or participate in creative activities.

Also, in adolescence, internal motivation is formed (for example, testing oneself, striving to learn something new). They can be a preparation for a person's future success. Motivation during this period is based on personal interests and needs.

The period of youth and adulthood-the period of youth and adulthood is an important period in the development of personality, during which motivation becomes more complicated. Choosing one's own professional activity, getting an education, starting a family, social relationships, and achieving personal goals all play an important role in the motivation process. During this period, motivation will be more related to internal factors. For example, ideas such as self-awareness, developing one's own abilities, and benefiting society through work enhance an individual's internal motivation. In addition, various successes and failures are also considered as part of the motivational process. At the same

² Vygotsky L.S. *Psychology of Art, Moscow: Peter, 1999, p. 270.*

³ Deci EL, Ryan RM. *Self-determination theory: A macro theory of human motivation development, and health. Canadian Psychology 2008.*

time, a person's determination and ability to make decisions to overcome difficulties on the way to achieving their goals play an important role.⁴

Old age-motivation can change in old age, but its importance remains indisputable. A person's motivation during this period is often related to their own health, useful service to society, or strengthening family ties. In old age, internal motivation is required, that is, to think about your goals and dreams, to spend time effectively and to develop relationships with others. However, self-awareness and self-acceptance are also important during this period.

The personal and social significance of motivation is the personal significance of motivation, which consists in helping an individual achieve their goals. Thanks to motivation, a person will be able to make full use of their inner strength, overcome difficulties and achieve success in various aspects of life. However, motivation is also important for society, as it helps to increase people's social responsibility, work effectively and develop society⁵.

Various motivation factors-Motivation is based on various factors: internal (previous experience, self-interests and goals) and external (incentive rewards, recognition) factors. The interaction of these factors forms the motivation of a personality and leads it to success. In order for a person to succeed, it is necessary to properly balance his internal and external factors.

Personality development is a process of spiritual, social, intellectual and psychological growth of a person. In every period, especially among young people and adults, motivation and its influence are important factors of development. Motivation is a person's desire and ability to make efforts to achieve their goals. The importance of the motivational process varies in different periods of personality development, and the effective organization of this process has a great impact on the overall development of personality.

Motivation changes at each stage of personality development and serves as the main mechanism necessary for human change and growth in different periods. The importance of motivation in different age periods of personality:

- ✓ In childhood: develops interest in reading and learning, self-confidence.
- ✓ In youth: motivation plays a big role in choosing a career and setting your course.
- ✓ In old age: internal motivation and understanding of the purpose of life are central.

The influence of motivation on all processes of personality development and its path to success is enormous. Understanding and adapting to a person's motivation system at different age periods helps them achieve the highest results.

Conclusion

Motivation in different periods of personality development is the main factor influencing the specific and continuous development of a person. Motivation guides a person's efforts to achieve goals at every young age, increases his self-confidence and helps him grow socially, psychologically and emotionally. In each age period, motivation has its own characteristics and significance and forms a significant part of the overall process of personality development.

At the same time, throughout the entire period of childhood and adolescence, adolescence and middle age, and old age, motivation at each stage of personality development is the main force in achieving a person's goals, shaping his actions. From childhood to old age, motivation helps a person to realize himself, master new abilities and successfully complete various life tasks. A proper understanding of the importance of motivation in personal development and its application in different periods of time allows a person to successfully achieve high goals.

⁴ Psychology of development. Pedagogical psychology of Z.T.Nishonova, N.G.Kamilova, D.U.Abdullayeva, publishing house "National Society of Philosophers of Uzbekistan".

⁵ *Motivation: a condition, a character trait, or both*., *Motivation, Effort, and a Neural Network Model*, 2020.

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